

IOT BASED NOISE DETECTION AND MANAGEMENT FOR SMART CITY

Gagana s channalli¹ Puneeth BR² Saraswathi R Devadiga³

¹Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Department of MCA , Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

²Nitte Deemed to be University, Department of MCA, NMAM Institute of Technology, Nitte, Karnataka, India.

³Shree Devi Institute of Technology, Department of MCA, Mangalore, Karnataka, India.

Abstract: Air and noise pollution are escalating issues that demand continuous monitoring to ensure a healthy and safe environment. The rapid expansion of infrastructure and industrial plants has heightened the need for intelligent monitoring systems. The Internet of Things (IoT) has gained immense popularity due to its cost-effectiveness, efficiency, and versatility, making it an ideal solution for addressing these challenges. IoT facilitates seamless communication between devices and humans, bridging the gap between human-machine interactions. Traditionally, data collection involved laborious field trips to various locations, followed by time-consuming analysis. However, the integration of internet-connected sensors and microcontrollers has revolutionized environmental parameter monitoring, making it more flexible, accurate, and efficient. This paper explores the potential of IoT-based smart monitoring systems in effectively monitoring air and noise pollution, emphasizing the advantages of real-time data collection, remote accessibility, and automated analysis. The implementation of such systems can significantly contribute to efficient environmental management and enable timely interventions to mitigate pollution and safeguard public health.

Keywords: IoT, Noise detection, Noise management, Smart cities, Air pollution, Environmental monitoring, Internet of Things, Sensor networks, Real-time monitoring.

I. INTRODUCTION

Pollution poses significant threats to human health, the environment, and the overall well-being of societies. It is responsible for causing cardiovascular and respiratory diseases, as well as cancer, making it the leading environmental cause of premature death in the European Union (EU). Certain substances found in pollution, such as arsenic, cadmium, nickel, and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons, are known to be human genotoxic carcinogens, meaning they can cause genetic damage that may lead to cancer. Importantly, there is no identified threshold below which these substances do not pose a risk [1][2].

In addition to its impact on human health, pollution, specifically air pollution, has detrimental effects on water and soil quality and disrupts ecosystems. Excess nitrogen pollution from air pollution leads to eutrophication, which disrupts the balance of nutrients in water and negatively affects aquatic life. Acid rain, another consequence of air pollution, damages soil and further harms ecosystems [3][4][5].

Although there has been progress in reducing air pollution levels in Europe, the EU's long-term objective of achieving air quality that does not significantly harm human health and the environment remains at risk. Air quality standards are frequently violated, particularly in urban areas known as "air pollution hotspots," where the majority of Europeans reside. Fine particles, nitrogen dioxide, and ground-level ozone are currently the most problematic pollutants [6][7][8].

Noise pollution is also a concern in the EU, with an estimated 20% of the population being exposed to unacceptable noise levels. This excessive noise adversely affects quality of life, causing stress, sleep disturbances, and various health issues, including cardiovascular problems. Wildlife is also impacted by noise pollution[9].

Addressing pollution and its various forms is crucial to safeguarding human health, protecting the environment, and promoting a better quality of life for all. It requires concerted efforts to reduce pollution levels, enforce air quality standards, and mitigate the harmful effects on both humans and wildlife [10].

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

"U-Air: When Urban Air Quality Inference Meets Big Data" by A. V. Donkelaar et al. [11] investigates the variation of air quality in urban areas, emphasizing the non-linear relationship with factors such as meteorology, traffic volume, and land use. The study highlights the advantages of achieving more accurate

and effective results with high performance. However, it also acknowledges the limitations of obtaining less accurate results and lower performance. The "Inferring Air Quality for Station Location Recommendation Based on Urban Big Data" by T. H. Cormen et al. [12] addresses the challenges associated with inferring air quality in locations where sufficient air-quality data for model training is lacking. The study proposes a semi-supervised inference model that incorporates existing monitoring data and diverse urban dynamics, including meteorology, human mobility, road networks, and points of interest (POIs). Additionally, an entropy-minimization model is proposed to suggest optimal locations for establishing new monitoring stations. The study demonstrates the advantages of this approach, such as minimizing inference error and model uncertainty, leading to increased effectiveness. However, the study also highlights the disadvantages related to the limited availability of air quality data, which can impact the accuracy of results, as well as the high cost associated with setting up new monitoring stations. The "Spatio-temporal Interpolation Methods for Air Pollution Exposure" by Gao et al. [13] focuses on investigating spatiotemporal interpolation methods for assessing air pollution, specifically fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5}). The study examines the impact of different time scales when applying a shape function-based method. By comparing the accuracy of interpolation results, the study identifies the most effective time scale for performing PM_{2.5} interpolations. The advantages of this study lie in the simultaneous integration of space and time, resulting in improved accuracy, and enabling the exploration of the relationship between air quality and population health outcomes. However, the study acknowledges the limitations of treating space and time separately, which can affect result accuracy, and highlights the need for better handling of the interpolation problem.

III. ANALYSIS

It gives the information regarding analysis done for the proposed system. It also provides the information regarding the existing system and also the need for the proposed system. The key features of the proposed system and the requirement specifications of the proposed system are discussed below.

- Gas sensor
- Temperature BMP18
- Humidity Sensor
- Breadboard
- Connectors
- Micro USB to USB cable

Gas sensor: In this project, to monitor the air pollution and to determine the air quality index, a gas sensor, MQ8 is used. MQ8, gas sensor operates at 5V voltage and 40 mA current. This sensor is chosen for its wide detecting scope, fast response, high sensitivity, stable and long life and lastly, a simple drive circuit.

Fig.1 :MQ135 Gas sensor

LM393 Sound Sensor: It has two independent voltage comparators that are made to operate from a one power supply over a large range of voltages. Operation from two supplies also is possible if the difference between the two supplies varies in 2 V to 36 V, and VCC is at least 1.5 V more positive

Fig.2 : LM393 Sound Sensor

DHT11 Temperature and Humidity Sensor: DHT11 is a humidity and temperature sensor. It can be used to monitor the temperature and humidity levels in a region. It can be interfaced with a Raspberry Pi module and can give immediate results. In this project, we are using this sensor to monitor the varying humidity and temperature levels.

Fig 3: Humidity Sensor

IV. METHODOLOGY

Fig 4 : Methodology

Fig 4 : circuit diagram

- Microcontroller unit is interfaced with various sensors like Gas Sensors, temperature, humidity, etc and telemetry operation is performed.
- Wi-Fi Transceiver module is used to transmit all the sensed parameter to the cloud and data is relayed from cloud to web application and vice versa. Clients (MCU) and Python application is based on HTTP PROTOCOL.
- In Python application user has to feed the training dataset and which will be used to build Machine Learning model. This system uses Decision Tree Algorithm to build the model.
- In Python application is built using Anaconda Framework with Jupyter Notebook IDE.

Fig 5: Data flow diagram

- This system is an IOT based where we are using embedded unit, IOT cloud and python application.
- An embedded system consists of micro controller, gas sensor, sound sensor and WiFi sensor.
- Once embedded system is turn ON it has to collect the data from sensor and update it in IOT cloud.
- Web based app has to fetch the data from IOT cloud and store in MySQL database.
- The data from sensor are treated as test data which will provide into validation model and get the prediction result.
- Web App should have training model which will read data set, preprocess the dataset and develop the validation model.

Fig.6: Kit used

Data Collection & Pre-processing: The first step in the methodology involves data collection and pre-processing. During this stage, relevant data is collected, ensuring its quality and integrity. Various sources, such as sensors or databases, may be used to gather the required data. Once collected, the data undergoes pre-processing steps to prepare it for further analysis. This may include tasks like data cleaning, handling missing values, normalizing or standardizing variables, and feature engineering.

Table 1: data set details

TEMP	Hum	CO	CO2	CH4
16	2.1	0.8	11	178
16	2.1	0.71	8	163
15	2	0.66	6.5	147
15	2	0.53	5.5	131
14	2	0.5	5.7	112
14	2	0.57	5.8	103
14	2	0.61	6.5	104
14	2	0.59	6.8	111
14	2	0.6	5.9	111
15	2	0.55	5.2	100
15	2	0.55	5.2	100

Model Training: After the data has been collected and pre-processed, the next step is model training. In this stage, the Random Forest classifier algorithm is employed. Random Forest is a supervised learning algorithm that builds multiple decision trees and combines them to obtain more accurate and stable predictions. Each decision tree is trained using a subset of the data, and the predictions from individual trees are then aggregated to make the final prediction. The Random Forest algorithm is known for its simplicity and ability to handle both classification and regression tasks.

Model Validation: Once the Random Forest model has been trained, it needs to be validated to assess its performance and generalization capabilities. Model validation is crucial to ensure that the trained model can effectively make predictions on unseen data. Various evaluation metrics, such as accuracy, precision, recall, or F1-score, can be used to evaluate the model's performance. Cross-validation techniques, such as k-fold cross-validation, may also be employed to obtain more robust performance estimates by partitioning the data into multiple subsets for training and validation.

Predict Result using Real-Time Data: After successful model validation, the trained Random Forest model can be used to predict results using real-time data. Incoming data is pre-processed using the same steps applied during training to ensure consistency. The ensemble of decision trees within the Random Forest

generates predictions based on the input data. The model takes into account the collective knowledge of the decision trees to make accurate predictions on new, unseen instances.

Parameter Tuning: Parameter tuning is an important aspect of optimizing the Random Forest classifier's performance. By adjusting the algorithm's hyperparameters, the model's effectiveness can be improved. Different hyperparameter settings are explored to find the best combination that maximizes performance on the given task. Techniques like grid search or random search can be employed to systematically search through the hyperparameter space and identify the optimal settings.

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In [57]: data.head()
Out[57]:
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	TEMP	Hum	CO	CO2	CH4	label
0	16.0	2.1	0.79	12.0	177.0	3
1	18.0	2.1	0.80	11.0	178.0	3
2	16.0	2.1	0.71	8.0	163.0	3
3	15.0	2.0	0.66	6.5	147.0	2
4	15.0	2.0	0.53	5.5	131.0	2

```
In [58]: data.describe()
Out[58]:
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	TEMP	Hum	CO	CO2	CH4	label
count	7000.000000	7000.000000	7000.000000	7000.000000	7000.000000	7000.000000
mean	24.609955	1.987586	0.577303	3.751814	45.884714	0.311857
std	5.964469	0.182813	0.336941	2.505342	98.705825	0.522671
min	7.000000	0.000000	0.060000	0.200000	0.000000	0.000000
25%	15.000000	1.900000	0.360000	2.100000	29.000000	0.000000
50%	26.000000	2.000000	0.500000	3.300000	40.000000	0.000000
75%	29.000000	2.000000	0.710000	4.700000	54.000000	1.000000
max	37.000000	3.800000	5.900000	32.000000	5004.000000	4.000000

Fig 7:

Fig 8:

V. RESULTS

Fig 9

Fig 10

VI. CONCLUSION

The proposed system comprises three key components: a hardware unit, an IoT cloud, and a software unit. The hardware unit is responsible for acquiring environmental data and storing it in the IoT cloud. The software unit retrieves the data from the cloud and feeds it into the validation model to generate predictions. This system effectively fulfills the functional requirements and provides a smart and cost-efficient solution for monitoring the environment. The inclusion of different models in this study contributes to its efficiency and effectiveness. The collected data holds significant value for future analysis and can be easily shared with other end users. Furthermore, this model can be expanded to monitor pollution in developing cities and industrial zones, making it a valuable tool for pollution monitoring purposes.

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